

Compressive Resistance Tests on Welded High-Strength Steel Columns

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ABSTRACT

European standards pertaining to design rules and recommendations for steel structures have been under revision in recent years with aim to improve the ease of use, increase harmonisation, to cover aspects of assessment, re-use and retrofitting of existing structures. In this process, rules covering the use of steels with yield strength above 460 MPa and up to 700 MPa have been included in EN 1993-1-1. Steels above 700 MPa and up to 960 MPa will be included in the upcoming version of EN 1993-1-12. The use of such steels has increased steadily over the last few decades because they allow for more light-weighted solutions than conventional steels. However, the material reduction inherent to such solutions increases structural slenderness, which in turn has implications for the bearing capacity of compressed members. Flexural buckling is one of the challenges that must be addressed when designing steel elements subject to compression. In Europe, the design flexural buckling resistance of a steel member is calculated using an equivalent imperfection factor based on the section type, fabrication method, and steel grade. This study presents a test campaign at Luleå University of Technology where 11 welded H-sections were tested in centric compression of which four were manufactured with S355 and seven with S960. The specimens were chosen to fill a gap in the literature data due to a lack of reported experimental tests on high-strength steel welded H-sections with nominal yield strengths above 700 MPa.

Keywords: flexural buckling, high-strength steel, experimental study, European standards.

1 INTRODUCTION

The term 'high-strength steel' requires additional clarification because it has been attributed to several different steel grades over time. At present, it typically refers to structural steel grades S460 and above. In Europe, structural steels with yield strengths $f_y \geq 460$ MPa are regarded as high-strength steels (HSS), while steels with $f_y \geq 700$ MPa are referred to as very high-strength steel (VHSS)(1). The uptake of HSS plates and members in the construction industry is still comparatively limited; the main markets for HSS at present are in automotive and crane manufacturing, both of which are industries where material weight is profoundly important. However, the benefits of using high-strength materials can extend beyond simple reductions in weight. For example, when selecting structural solutions, considerable efforts have been made to reduce material usage in recent years because of environmental concerns.

Projects finalised before 2009 that used HSS in structures including bridges, trusses, and high-rise structures have been reviewed by other authors (2–4). A more recent overview of construction works that made use of VHSS can be found in (5). To identify factors limiting the use of HSS, Alriksson and Henningson (6) surveyed steel industry stakeholders (both producers and users) in Sweden. Their results indicated that a major barrier to the wider use of new steel grades is a lack of standards and norms.

The second-generation Eurocode 3 part 1-1 incorporates the design rules from EN 1993-1-12 that covered steel grades between S460 and S700. The changes that concern flexural buckling recommends the use of more favourable buckling curves only for rolled and hot-finished HSS sections. For example, in the case of rolled sections with a height over width ratio $H/B \leq 1.2$ and a flange thickness $t_f \leq 100$ mm, curve b may be used instead of curve c for flexural buckling over the weak axis, and curve a may be used instead of curve b for flexural buckling over the strong axis. No changes are proposed for welded or cold-formed sections. This approach can be considered conservative based on its underlying model of residual stresses in welded and hot rolled/finished sections (7). However, the relative increase in resistance for steel up to and including S700 was not considered sufficient to justify the update to a more favourable buckling curve.

The main products in VHSS steels are plates of various thickness with good welding and cold-forming properties. This is the preferred choice for steel manufacturers because of the larger market share and the simplicity and reliability of the manufacturing process. Therefore, it is interesting to assess the buckling performance of welded and cold-formed sections in VHSS grades.

This study aims at presenting the compressive test results from 11 welded H-sections that were tested in centric compression of which four were manufactured with S355 and seven with S960. The specimens were chosen to fill a gap in the literature data due to a lack of reported experimental tests on high-strength steel welded H-sections with nominal yield strengths above 700 MPa. The first part of the paper briefly presents the data available in literature related to compressive tests on welded section made of VHSS. The second part of the paper focuses on the experimental campaign and the outcome of the tests and finally the experimental results are presented and compared to data available in literature.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the first researchers to investigate flexural-buckling capacity of welded steel profiles with $f_y \geq 600$ MPa were Rasmussen and Hancock (8,9). Their study covered 12 welded H-sections and 13 box sections. The test results were then compared with the Australian, American, British, and European buckling curves. Their study concluded that in the current form the design standards are conservative, and the Australian, American, and British standards can be safely applied. Additionally, the authors proposed to assign buckling curve a instead of c in the European standards for weak axis buckling of welded box and H-sections made of HSS with plate thickness $t \leq 40$ mm.

Ban et al. (10) tested six welded box and H-sections manufactured with steel with nominal $f_y = 960$ MPa. The welded H-sections had Class 4 flanges, and thus an additional reduction of the compressive resistance was expected due to local buckling. The two specimens tested in eccentric compression do not represent valid comparisons to the flexural buckling curves and were not considered in the current study. The authors concluded that the EN 1993-1-1(11) buckling curve a would be applicable to 960 MPa HSS columns. The authors recommended that upon further research, a value of $\alpha = 0.16$ instead of 0.21 might be applied.

Additional 12 centrally compressed welded box and H-sections were reported (12). The columns were manufactured using complete penetration welding, thus leading to a different residual stress distribution. Two columns were reported to be straightened by flame heating and were disregarded herein. The authors concluded that buckling curve a would fit the experimental observations better than curve c. However, due to the limited amount of performed tests the authors recommend further research in form of numerical simulations.

Ma et al. (13) reported results from seven centrally compressed welded H-sections manufactured from S690. The specimens covered a range of slenderness from 0.77 to 1.41 with cross-section in class 1 to 3 all of which were included in the analysis. Their study concluded that the design rules provided by the EN 1993-1-1 (11) underestimated the buckling resistances of slender columns of S690 steel welded H-sections, and thus recommended the use of a different buckling curve with an increased structural efficiency. Unlike the European standard, the resistance computed using the

AISC 360 was found to be close to the measured failure load and applicable for the design of slender columns of S690 welded H-sections.

The material and geometrical properties of the welded I/H-sections discussed in the current section have been reported in (14) and concluded that the EN 1993-1-1(11) underestimates the flexural buckling resistance of HSS welded I/H-sections by 30%. The reported difference is an average value and cannot be generalised for the entire slenderness range. Furthermore, the conclusion was based on test results from columns manufactured with steel grades from S690 up to S960.

Compressive tests on welded I/H sections made of S960 steel (15) and S690 (16,17) steels that were not included in (14) concluded that the current design curves for flexural buckling of welded I/H sections are conservative. The outcome of the tests is compared with the EN 1993-1-1 flexural buckling curve c in Fig. 1 with the reduction factor χ and the non-dimensional slenderness $\bar{\lambda}$ computed based on the measured geometrical and material properties reported in the literature presented in this section.

- S690 (Ma et al)
- Q690 (Li et al)
- S690 (Khan et al)
- S960 (Ban et al)
- S690 (Sun et al)
- S960 (Su and Zhao)
- S690 (Rasmussen & Hancock)
- S690 (Filho et al)

Fig. 1. Comparison of the compressive test results extracted from literature and the EN 1993-1-1 flexural buckling curve c for a) S690 and b) S960 steels.

3 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

3.1 Scope

At the time the testing presented in this study was performed only 2 compressive tests performed on welded I/H sections were found in technical literature (10) in the slenderness range 1,2 to 2,0 that had weak axis buckling as failure mode. The aim of the experimental work presented herein was to assess if I/H welded sections made of steel grades with nominal yield strength $f_{yn} \geq 960$ MPa steel could be designed using more favourable flexural buckling curves due to the reduced residual stresses arising from manufacturing compared steel grades with $f_{yn} \leq 460$ MPa. The residual stresses are known to have the highest influence on the compressive resistance of structural members in the medium slenderness range $\bar{\lambda} = 0,6$ to 1,0. The residual stresses were also assessed on one welded specimen to validate this assumption (5)

3.2 Experimental layout

A total of 11 welded H-sections were tested in centric compression, of which four were manufactured with S355 and seven with S960. The specimens were chosen to fill a gap in the literature data due to a lack of reported experimental tests on HSS welded H-sections with nominal yield strengths $f_{yn} > 700$ MPa. One additional S960 specimen was manufactured for residual stress measurement.

S960 columns were designed with two different cross-section sizes to evaluate the effect of the local slenderness on the compressive resistance without introducing local instabilities. The specimens were classified as class 1 and class 2 cross-sections according to EN 1993-1-1(11), with the flange being the limiting criterion. Four reference specimens made from S355 were also tested. Two of the reference specimens (H1-S355-06 and H1¹-S355-06) had the same cross-section as the S960 columns. The remaining two (H1²-S355-06 and H2-S355-06) were designed to have the same flange $\bar{\lambda}_f$ and web slenderness $\bar{\lambda}_w$ as the S960 columns.

An overview of the geometric and cross-sectional properties of the tested columns is provided in (5) and are summarised in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Nominal geometric and material properties of the tested specimens

Label	H	B	t_f	t_w	L_{cr}	A	I_y	I_z	f_{yn}
	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)	(m)	(mm ²)	(cm ⁴)	(cm ⁴)	(MPa)
H1-S960-06	100	100	10	6	0.81	2480	432	167	960
H2-S960-06	110	110	10	6	0.90	2740	588	222	960
H1-S960-08	100	100	10	6	1.05	2480	432	167	960
H2-S960-08	110	110	10	6	1.15	2740	588	222	960
H1-S960-10	100	100	10	6	1.30	2480	432	167	960
H2-S960-10	110	110	10	6	1.41	2740	588	222	960
H1-S960-12	100	100	10	6	1.54	2480	432	167	960
H2-S960-12	110	110	10	6	1.68	2740	588	222	960
H1-S355-06	100	100	10	6	1.30	2480	432	167	355
H1 ¹ -S355-06	110	110	10	6	1.41	2740	588	222	355
H1 ² -S355-06	150	150	10	6	1.86	3780	1582	563	355
H2-S355-06	160	160	10	6	1.97	4040	1940	683	355

The test setup was configured in accordance with the recommendations described in (18) and the ECCS testing procedure (19). The load was applied to maintain a constant strain rate of 0.1 %/min, in keeping with the ECCS column testing program.

A total of 13 strain gauges were installed on each tested column, positioned on the outside of the outermost point of each flange at three locations over the column's length; an additional gauge was installed in the middle section of the flange. A schematic depiction of the test setup is presented in *Fig. 2*. The horizontal displacement was monitored using three LVDTs positioned at distances of $L/4$ from the end plates. Additionally, the end-rotations over the buckling axis were monitored using a

digital image correlation (DIC) system to validate the assumed effective length and the corresponding buckling shape.

Fig. 2. Test setup a) Sketch and b) Photo

3.3 Material properties

A total of 12 tensile tests were performed to determine the material properties, three for each combination of thickness ($t = 6$ and 10 mm) and steel grade (S355, S960). The actual geometry was measured for each coupon using a digital micrometre. The tensile tests were conducted under strain rate control based on feedback from an extensometer over the parallel length at a rate of $\dot{\epsilon}_{Le} = 2,5 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. The average values of the upper yield strength R_{eH} , the tensile strength R_m , and the elastic modulus E were later used as characteristic values when evaluating the calculated resistance and the non-dimensional slenderness. The stress-strain curves from the tensile tests are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 along with the properties characterising the steel grade.

Fig. 3. Tensile test results for S355

Fig. 4. Tensile test results for S960

3.4 Compressive test results

The recorded load-displacement response of the tested struts at the mid-point v is shown in Fig. 5. The test results are also summarised in Table 2.

The results show that the N_u/N_{pl} ratio for class 2 cross-sections was highest for slenderness values $\bar{\lambda} < 1.2$. Similar results were obtained for welded MSS H-sections by Fukumoto and Itoh (20) when comparing different section sizes to ECCS curve b . This increase in strength can be attributed to the effect of the residual stresses on the flexural buckling resistance in this slenderness range. At higher $\bar{\lambda}$ values, the resistance depends mainly on the elastic resistance, which is governed by factors such as geometric properties, the elastic modulus, and the boundary conditions.

Fig. 5. Normalised load-displacement curves for tested specimens

Specimen H1-S960-12 exhibited a higher N_u/N_{pl} ratio than H2-S960-12, mainly due to a smaller initial out-of-straightness and a greater contribution from buckling mode 2. The contribution from buckling mode 2 is likely due to the difference in length on the four corners of the column. The length of the tested specimens is reported in (5).

Table 2. Flexural buckling resistance of the tested specimens

Label	$\bar{\lambda}_z$ (-)	N_{pl} (kN)	N_u (kN)	$\chi = N_u/N_{pl}$ (-)
H1-S960-06	0.698	2497	2096	0.840
H1-S960-08	0.914	2489	2099	0.843
H2-S960-08	0.908	2752	2425	0.881
H1-S960-10	1.134	2480	1833	0.739
H2-S960-10	1.108	2762	2240	0.811
H1-S960-12	1.338	2497	1582	0.634
H2-S960-12	1.312	2811	1670	0.594
H1-S355-06	0.724	1010	678	0.671
H11-S355-06	0.709	1115	764	0.685
H12-S355-06	0.693	1544	1097	0.710
H2-S355-06	0.694	1654	1163	0.703

The test results and the results collected from literature are compared to the EN 1993-1-1 buckling curves *a* and *c* in Fig. 6. The figure shows that the curve *a* can be considered as a safe sided choice for welded I/H-sections made of steels with $f_{yn} \geq 690$ MPa. The values presented in Fig. 6 are computed based on the average measured values. The use of nominal material values for the modulus of elasticity and the steels yield strength to compute the compressive resistance normally results in an increase in safety, but it also increases the scatter of the computed resistance relative to the selected design curve.

Fig. 6. Comparison of calculated and test resistances based on averaged measured values for the tested specimens a) Steel grades with $f_{yn} \geq 690$ MPa and b) $f_{yn} \geq 960$ MPa.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This article briefly describes the experimental campaign and the test results from 11 welded H-sections that were tested in centric compression of which four were manufactured with S355 and seven with S960. The specimens were chosen to fill a gap in the literature data due to a lack of reported experimental tests on high-strength steel welded H-sections with nominal yield strengths above 700 MPa.

The EN 1993-1-1(21) is currently providing conservative computed resistance values for HSS and VHSS welded I/H-sections. This has also been concluded by other researchers who performed compressive tests on such sections and/or numerically assessed their performance, e.g. (10,13,15,16). The conservative estimation is mainly due to the underlying formulation of the buckling curves that are based on an equivalent geometrical imperfection to account for the influence of residual stresses. The residual stresses have been shown to have a reduced magnitude relative to the yield stress in steels with $f_{yn} \geq 690$ MPa (12,22–26) than in mild steels with $f_{yn} \leq 460$ MPa resulting in more conservative computed values for the flexural buckling resistance of section made of HSS. A change in the EN 1993-1-1(21) buckling curve for welded I/H-sections from the currently referenced curve *c* to curve *a* would encourage the use of HSS and could also generate significant material saving. This in turn would also benefit the environmental impact of new constructions.

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